

Magnetic Field Cancellation Techniques for the Mars Global Surveyor Solar Array

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Abstract

The Mars Global Surveyor spacecraft carries a sensitive magnetometer system to detect and characterize the intrinsic magnetic field of Mars, if one exists. The use of booms to place the sensors remote from the spacecraft was not possible due to resource constraints. Instead, the sensors were mounted at the outer edge of the solar array, in close proximity to strings of solar cells. The current geometry in the array was optimized with a piecewise linear simulation to minimize the magnetic field generated at the sensor by the circulating currents under all operating conditions. A number of novel techniques were used in achieving magnetic field cancellation including carefully chosen circuit path lengths with zero area in selected strings, and sensitive magnetic verification tests in the Earth's field with a resolution of 1 part in 200,000. The results show that the field generated by the array at the sensor location during the Mars mapping phase of the mission and under nominal conditions will be less than 0.4 to 0.6 nT ($1 \text{ nT} = 10^{-5} \text{ Gauss}$) under full solar illumination. The design is also reasonably tolerant of string failures. This major achievement would not have been possible without a close and synergistic interaction among the manufacturer, scientists and spacecraft engineers during the design, simulation and test of the solar array.

Introduction

The accurate measurement of weak magnetic fields aboard spacecraft is an art that requires a systematic approach to the reduction and elimination of sources of magnetic fields associated with spacecraft subsystems (Ness, 1970; Harten and Clark, 1995). The errors introduced by stray spacecraft fields, both static and dynamic can be very large unless appropriate measures are implemented for their control and reduction. This represents a very significant systems engineering challenge which reaches into all aspects of the spacecraft and subsystems design and verification process. Since weak stray magnetic fields are normally of no consequence for the correct functional operation of these systems, the imposition of **magnetic cleanliness requirements** on electronic and mechanical components creates a new set of challenges which can increase costs significantly if implemented without the benefit of prior experience and extensive systems

engineering knowledge. Due to budgetary constraints, this problem has become a dominating factor in contemporary space missions. Classical and time-honored magnetic cleanliness approaches such as the use of booms to place sensors remote from the spacecraft, materials control to avoid use of ferromagnetic materials, and electrical and mechanical design constraints to minimize the generation of dynamic fields by electrical currents and moving mechanical parts, although extremely effective, are no longer considered essential in a project due to their potential cost and schedule impact.

Faced with these constraints, scientists who are interested in these measurements have become intimately involved in the spacecraft design process, right from the start, to contribute with their experience to the achievement of the difficult engineering tradeoffs necessary to carry out viable magnetic measurements on spacecraft built without significant magnetic cleanliness requirements. The case of the Mars Global Surveyor spacecraft and the accommodation of the Magnetic Fields Investigation sensors on the solar array panels is presented in this paper as an example of a successful design tradeoff.

The Mars Global Surveyor Spacecraft

Mars Global Surveyor (MGS) has been designed as a replacement for the Mars Observer (MO) spacecraft lost in 1993 just after the activation of the propulsion system before Mars orbit insertion. It is generally accepted that MO experienced a catastrophic failure when propulsion system isolation valves were activated. MGS will be launched in November 1996 aboard a McDonnell Douglas Delta II rocket which has a more limited capability in terms of injected mass at Mars than the Titan III used for Mars Observer. Therefore, the long deployable boom used in MO for the magnetic field sensors which weighed some 18 kilograms, could not be used. To achieve orbit insertion with minimal fuel usage MGS uses the large area of the solar array (approx. 12 m^2) to reduce the velocity of the spacecraft by aerobraking against the Martian atmosphere. The large dimensions of the solar array required to generate sufficient power at Mars make it an ideal candidate as a substitute for a long boom to place the MAG sensors at a significant distance (4 meters) from the spacecraft

body. This configuration simplifies the issue of spacecraft magnetic cleanliness but the currents circulating in the array when illuminated can generate very large magnetic fields unless proper precautions are adopted in the design. To survive the heating caused by aerobraking string and cell interconnects wiring are carried entirely on only one side of the solar panels. This simplifies the analysis and makes possible a strategy that results in minimum magnetic field at the location of the magnetometer sensors. As part of an accommodation agreement, the magnetic field experimenters were allowed to work closely with the spacecraft and solar array designers early in the development and test phase. This resulted in a very successful and efficient interaction which yielded the desired results at minimum cost and impact to the MGS project.

Magnetic Field Cancellation in the MGS Solar Array

As mentioned previously, the MGS array is unique in the sense that it is used for aerobraking the spacecraft at Mars. The elevated temperatures that result from this interaction dictated that all wiring associated with the solar array be placed on only the cell side of the supporting panel (constructed using a composite of carbon fiber epoxy, Kevlar and aluminum honeycomb core). The back side of the substrate faces the ram flow direction and can reach elevated temperatures during aerobraking. If a vector magnetometer sensor is mounted parallel to the plane of the substrate and such that the center of the sensor triad is aligned with the plane of the solar cells and wiring, then the currents circulating in the array will generate magnetic fields which only have components **perpendicular** to the solar panels. This geometry simplifies considerably the magnetic field cancellation challenge reducing it effectively to a one dimensional problem.

The solar cell strings in the MGS array have been placed out perpendicular to the center line joining the two hinged panels to the spacecraft. The strings are also partially shunted during excess power generation situations creating additional and variable current paths which must be taken into account during compensation calculations. Preliminary calculations for a magnetometer sensor mounted along the center line, at the outer edge of the array and 30 cm. away from the outermost solar cell string, indicated that sufficient cancellation could be achieved for the inboard panel (GaAs) using nearly symmetrical circuits of equal areas in which currents circulate in opposite directions. This is due to the fact that this panel is distant from the magnetometer sensor and magnetic field gradients are small. However this was not true for the outboard panel particularly for those cell strings located within 1.5 meters of the magnetometer sensor. Figure 1 illustrates a simple "side wiring" magnetic field cancellation scheme which works well when the distances involved

are much larger than the separation between the return wire and the centerline of the cell string. The distributed field generated by the sheet currents flowing in the cells is cancelled by the magnetic field generated by the return current flowing in the opposite direction on the parallel side wiring. In the case of MGS, pairs of strings with currents flowing in opposite directions were compensated as shown in Figure 2. In spite of the apparent symmetry and expected cancellation, the fact that one of the current loops is closer to the magnetic field sensor than the other implies that there will exist a small residual field associated with each pair of strings. When many pairs are placed side by side the small residual fields add-up in the same direction to a sizeable contribution and need to be cancelled. This was achieved by enlarging the area of the compensation loop of the third pair of strings as measured from the outer edge of the array (see Figure 3). The enlarged compensation loop cancels out the net field created by the previous two pairs of strings.

All analytical calculations for the MGS array were carried out using the expression for the magnetic field of a line current of finite linear dimension,

$$B = \mu_0 I (\cos\alpha - \cos\beta) / 4\pi r$$

where B is perpendicular to the line current direction, and r and the angles α and β are defined in Figure 4. Beginning and endpoint coordinates were assigned to all wiring segments and sheet currents in the solar cell strings were modelled as multiple (six or more) line currents uniformly distributed across their widths. The early cancellation concepts were simulated and tested at the Goddard Space Flight Center Magnetic Test Facility using a mock-up of the solar panels with wide copper strips simulating the solar cell strings.

The unpaired strings of cells located within 60 cm of the magnetometer sensor required special compensation techniques to achieve the desired low residual field. The basic approach used is illustrated in Figure 5a, where a single string of cells with a split return running back along both sides is shown. For distances that are much larger than the cell width, the oppositely directed, symmetrical current flows produce no net magnetic field. At closer range, the loop closest to the sensor will generate a larger field than its counterpart further away and the balance is lost. The solution adopted for MGS was to increase the resistance of the closest path to decrease its associated magnetic field to a level identical to that of the more distant loop. This was easily achieved by increasing the length of the return wire by an amount calculated analytically to give

minimum field at the magnetometer sensor (Fig 5b). Since both return wires are joined close to the opposite end of the strand, are built with the same copper wire and are essential at the same temperature, the resistance ratios track very closely and excellent magnetic field compensation is obtained over a broad temperature range. Accurate placement of the conductors on the panel substrate to agree with assumptions made in the calculations is a must. For MGS all wiring was placed within 0.05 inches of the design specifications. Note also that trimming of the compensation scheme to zero magnetic field is extremely easy by adjusting the excess length of return wiring without disturbing the array.

The modified split return compensation scheme was used in all single strings near the magnetometer sensor, including those associated with shunt circuits. A qualification panel was manufactured and used to verify the initial design concepts. The lengths of the zero-area loops was adjusted to take into account manufacturing details and the actual routing of the interconnection wiring.

Magnetic Tests of the MGS Solar Array

Testing of the qualification and flight solar panels was carried out using contemporary magnetic field instrumentation designed at Goddard for this purpose. These instruments use synchronous sampling to achieve almost complete rejection of large and variable ambient magnetic fields associated with 60 HZ power systems and can detect very small fields ($0.2 \text{ nT} - 1 \text{ nT} = 10^{-5}$ Gauss) superimposed on the much larger ambient field. Due to the performance of this instrumentation it was not necessary to take the solar array to a magnetics test facility and the measurements were carried out right on the manufacturing floor. Since it is difficult to illuminate uniformly a large solar array, the cell strings were **forward biased** during the tests to force a current through the circuits and thus obtain an accurate assessment of the magnetic field generated by the array. By turning the biasing current ON and OFF a number of times a very accurate measurement of the field generated by the array was obtained. After correcting for stray fields associated with the test power supplies, the measured stray field generated by the solar array at the location of the magnetometer was less than 0.6 nT and considered satisfactory for the Mars application. Although the goal for MGS was 0.3nT total variability of the stray field due to all sources on the spacecraft, the achievement of the 0.6 nT level was considered a major success. No significant impacts on the quality of the Martian magnetic field data to be obtained by MGS are expected.

Summary and Acknowledgements

It is clear that the close and synergistic working relationship among experimenters, JPL, NASA,

Lockheed Martin Astronautics and SpectroLab personnel supported by the MGS Project was instrumental in the achievement of the significant results presented above. This effort has shown that "natural" spacecraft appendages (like solar arrays) can be used effectively as low cost alternatives to long deployable booms, even for sensitive missions like MGS.

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References

- Ness, N. F., "Magnetometers for Space Research", Space Science Reviews, 11, 459-554, 1970
- Harten, R. and Clark, K., "The Design Features of the GGS WIND and POLAR Spacecraft", Space Science Reviews, 71, 23-40, 1995

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

FIGURE 5 (A)

FIGURE 5 (B)